

Enhancing Visualization: Adjusting the Graphics Panel Background Color from Light to Dark and Vice Versa

Elena Gjorgjieva; Kiro Gjorgjiev

elena@simplegissoft.com ; kiro@simplegissoft.com ; info@simplegissoft.com

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People have different visual preferences, so giving them the option to adjust the background color makes the workspace more comfortable and user-friendly. Changing the background can also enhance how LiDAR point clouds or other data are displayed, making it easier to notice small details. For example, using a dark background might improve the contrast with lighter data points, making patterns easier to spot. Plus, staring at a bright background for hours can be tough on the eyes, and switching to a darker one can help ease that strain, especially in dim lighting.

This task is super simple—it's just a one-click feature in SGIS, designed to give users a more comfortable experience. Let's take a quick look at how to change the background color;

Fig. 1 Opening a LiDAR project in SGIS v.R.

We've opened a LiDAR project in SGIS v.R, and the dataset includes several classifications, one of which is class 1, or Unclassified. This class contains all the man-made objects like fences, cars, and streetlights, which are typically shown in white.

Since the default background of the graphics panel is white (or light), it can be hard to see these points clearly. To fix this, we'll switch the background to black (or dark),

making the points stand out more, which will help us process the data more accurately.

To change the background, we'll start by going to the 'View' menu in the main toolbar. From there, we'll click on 'Background Color', where we'll see three options: light, silver, and black.

Next, we'll choose the 'Black' option. As soon as we click it, the graphics panel will turn black, as shown in figure 3 and figure 4, making the LiDAR points much easier to see.

Fig. 2 Changing the background color in SGIS v.R. by selecting the 'Black' option from the 'Background Color' settings under the 'View' menu in the main toolbar.

Fig. 3 After selecting the 'Black' option, the graphics panel in SGIS v.R changes to a black background, enhancing the visibility of the LiDAR point cloud.

By zooming in on one of the tiles, we can see that the points are much clearer and easier to distinguish. The patterns really stand out now, allowing us to clearly identify bridges and the fences surrounding the buildings.

Additionally, if we disable the ground points, managing all the other classifications becomes significantly easier.

Fig. 4 Zoomed-in view of a tile in SGIS v.R, demonstrating enhanced clarity of LIDAR points. The clearer visualization makes it easier to identify patterns such as bridges and fences surrounding buildings.

Fig. 5 Demonstration of changing the graphics panel background to silver-gray in SGIS v.R. Users can navigate to the 'View' menu and select 'Background Color' to switch to the 'Silver' option.

If users prefer, they can choose to switch the background to silver, which will give the graphics panel a sleek silver-gray color.

To demonstrate this function, let's return to the main menu toolbar and head to the 'View' menu. From there, we'll click on 'Background Color' and select 'Silver.'

Once we do this, the color of the graphics panel will instantly change to silver-gray.

Fig. 6 The graphics panel in SGIS v.R instantly changes to silver-gray after selecting the 'Silver' option from the 'Background Color' settings.

Let's go through the procedure one more time to switch back to the default light color setting. With this step, we'll have completed the process.

Fig.7 The procedure is complete.